

Supplementary Information

Continuous Flow Decarboxylative Monofluoroalkylation Enabled by Photoredox Catalysis

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1 General information

^1H , ^{13}C and ^{19}F NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker AscendTM 400 spectrometer (400 MHz for ^1H , 101 MHz for ^{13}C , 377 MHz for ^{19}F). Chemical shifts (δ) are reported in parts per million (ppm) relatives to residual CHCl_3 (^1H : $\delta = 7.26$ ppm) and relative to CDCl_3 (^{13}C : $\delta = 77.16$ ppm). Spin-spin coupling constants (J) are given in Hz. Chemical shifts are reported in parts per million (ppm, δ) and reported to two decimal places for proton shifts, and one decimal place for carbon shifts. The multiplicity of the signals is reported as s (singlet), d (doublet), t (triplet), q (quartet), quin (quintet), br (broad signal), m (multiplet). As far as possible, complete and unambiguous assignment of all resonances was performed by combined application of 2D NMR techniques, i.e. HSQC and COSY experiments. NOESY experiments were performed for structural evaluations of the products. ^1H NMR on the reaction crude was used to establish the diastereomeric ratio. Thermoscientific Nicolet Summit PRO FTIR Spectrometer was employed to obtain the infrared spectra. Agilent 6530 accurate mass Q-TOF instrument and Excalibur data system were used to record the high resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) spectra. Flash column chromatography was performed using 40-63 μm mesh silica for chromatography under the reported conditions for each compound and using standard techniques. Solutions were concentrated under reduced pressure with a rotary evaporator under reduced pressure (0 –1000 mbar) with a bath temperature of 40°C. Aluminium sheets precoated with silica gel 60 F254 (Merck) were used for the thin layer chromatography (TLC). The spots were visualized under UV light ($\lambda = 254$ nm) or by oxidation with KMnO_4 (aq.). GC analyses were performed using a gas chromatograph (dimethylsilicon capillary column, 30 m, 0.25 mm i.d.) equipped with a mass selective detector operating at 70 eV (EI). Photochemical transformations were performed employing a ThalesNanoTM photocube device. The employed flow apparatus consisted of Harvard PHD 2000 syringe pumps, equipped with gastight syringes purchased from SGE. All the chemicals were purchased from Alfa Aesar, Sigma-Aldrich, Fluorochem, Fluka, BLDpharm and TCI Europe, and used without further purification unless otherwise specified.

2 α -fluoro carboxylic acids and SOMOphiles collection

2.1 α -fluoro carboxylic acids collection

The α -fluoro carboxylic acids **1a**, **1d** were prepared according to reported procedures.^{1,2,3} The α -fluoro carboxylic acids employed in this work are shown below.

Figure 1. Collection of employed α -fluoro carboxylic acids.

$^aE_{p/2}$ potentials listed are related to the carboxylate form of the corresponding acid.

2.2 SOMophile and Electrophile collection

The SOMophiles **S3a**, **S13-S16**, were prepared according to reported procedures.^{4,5,6,7,8} The SOMophiles (**S1a-S16**) and the Electrophiles (**S17a-S20**) employed in this work are shown below.

Figure 2. Collection of employed SOMophiles and Electrophiles.

2.3 Ineffective SOMOphiles

Figure 3. List of ineffective SOMOphiles.

3 Synthesis of photocatalyst and substrates

3.1 Synthesis of 2,4,5,6-tetrakis(carbazol-9-yl)-4,6-dicyanobenzene (4CzIPN)

To a flame-dried round bottom flask charged with a stir bar, were added carbazole (5.0 equiv., 12 mmol, 2.0 g) and dry THF (24 mL). The solution was cooled down to 0 °C and NaH (60% in mineral oil, 7.5 equiv., 18 mmol, 0.72 g) was slowly added under vigorous stirring. After 2 hours, tetrafluoroisophthalonitrile (1.0 equiv., 2.4 mmol, 0.48 g) was added and the mixture was stirred at room temperature overnight. A yellow precipitate progressively appeared. When TLC analysis showed a full conversion of the starting material, water (1 mL) was added dropwise under vigorous stirring to neutralize the excess of NaH, and the mixture was evaporated to give a yellow solid. The solid was successively washed with water and ethanol to afford 1.35 g (1.38 mmol, 71.3% yield) of spectroscopically pure 4CzIPN. Spectroscopic data are in agreement with those reported in literature.⁹

3.2 Synthesis and characterization of the substrates

3.2.1 Synthesis of 2-fluoro-4-phenylbutanoic acid (**1b**)

Under argon atmosphere, in a flamed-dried 50 mL round bottom flask charged with a stir bar, a solution of methyl 2-hydroxy-4-phenylbutanoate (3 g, 15.45 mmol) in THF (0.1 M) was added. A solution of Diethylaminosulfur trifluoride (DAST) (30.91 mmol, 4.1 ml (15%*m/m*)) in THF was added dropwise at 0°C and the reaction proceeded for 3h at room temperature. When TLC analysis showed a full conversion of the starting material, the crude was quenched with 50 mL of H₂O and washed three times with a 50mL of an aqueous solution of Na₂CO₃ (1M). The organic phase was dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered, concentrated under reduced pressure and methyl 2-fluoro-4-phenylbutanoate was obtained with a 90% yield (2.73 g, 13.90 mmol) and was used in the next step without any further purification. In a reaction flask charged with a solution of 2-fluoro-4-phenylbutanoate (2.73 g, 13.90 mmol) in THF:H₂O (1:1) mixture, LiOH (0.66 g, 27.8 mmol) was added and the reaction proceeded for 6h. The reaction mixture was washed with 50 mL of Et₂O for three times and the aqueous phase was acidified to pH 1 and extracted three times with diethyl ether. The organic phase was dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered, concentrated under reduced pressure. Compound **1b** was isolated as pale yellow solid in a 95% yield (2.40 g, 13.20 mmol) without any further purification.

Spectroscopic data matched those previously reported in the literature.¹⁰

4 Optimization

4.1 Photocatalyst optimization

PC1

PC2

PC3

PC4

Entry ^[a]	Photocatalyst	Yield (%) ^[b]
1	(PC1) Ir[dF(CF ₃)ppy] ₂ (dtbbpy))PF ₆	88
2	(PC1) Ir[dF(CF ₃)ppy] ₂ (dtbbpy))PF ₆ ^[a]	92
3	(PC2) 4CzIPN	88
4	(PC3) Mes ⁻ Acr ⁺ BF ₄ ⁻ ^[a]	5
5	(PC4) 2,4,6-Triphenylpyrylium tetrafluoroborate ^[a]	/
6	No photocatalyst	/

Table 1. ^[a] Reactions performed in DCM and Cs₂CO₃. ^[b] Determined by ¹H NMR analysis using CH₂Br₂ as internal standard.

4.2 Solvent and base optimization

Entry ^[a]	Solvent	Base	Yield (%) ^[a]
1	DMSO	K ₃ PO ₄	88
2	DMSO	Cs ₂ CO ₃	83
3	DMSO	2,6-Lutidine	77
4	DMSO	KOH	56
2	DMF	K ₃ PO ₄	85
6	DMF	Cs ₂ CO ₃	84
7	DMF	KOH	60
8	DMF	LiOH	27
3	ACN	K ₃ PO ₄	53
4	NMP	K ₃ PO ₄	38
5	THF	K ₃ PO ₄	5
5	DCM	Cs ₂ CO ₃	Tr.
8	Acetone	Cs ₂ CO ₃	Tr.
9	DMF	NaOH	/
6	THF	Cs ₂ CO ₃	/
7	MeOH	Cs ₂ CO ₃	/
8	DMSO	/	10

Table 2. ^[a] Determined by ¹H NMR analysis using CH₂Br₂ as internal standard.

Entry ^[a]	Concentration DMSO (M)	Yield (%) ^[a]
1	0.1	84
2	0.2	85
3	0.3	88

Table 3. ^[a] Determined by ¹H NMR analysis using CH₂Br₂ as internal standard.

4.3 Reaction time optimization

Entry ^[a]	Reaction time	Yield (%) ^[a]
1	30'	12
2	1h	22
3	3h	88
4	16h	88

Table 4. ^[a] Determined by ¹H NMR analysis using CH_2Br_2 as internal standard.

4.4 Irradiation power optimization

Entry ^[a]	Irradiation power	Yield (%) ^[a]
1	40 W	20
2	128 W	88
3	No light	/

Table 5. ^[a] Determined by ¹H NMR analysis using CH_2Br_2 as internal standard.

5 Batch experiment

5.1 General procedure 1 (GP1): radical fluoroxyalkylation in batch

To an oven-dried vial equipped with a stirring bar were added the α -fluoro acid (0.3 mmol, 1.3 equiv.), potassium phosphate tribasic (0.3 mmol, 1.3 equiv.), 4CzIPN (5.9 mg, 2.5 mol%), the SOMOphile (0.23 mmol, 1 equiv.) and dry DMSO (1 mL). Subsequently, the vial was sealed with a rubber septum and the solution was sparged with N_2 (1 min). The solution was stirred and irradiated in a PhotoCube™ photochemical reactor equipped with a blue lamp ($\lambda = 457$ nm, 128 W) for 16 h. Then the vial was removed from the photochemical reactor. The solution was diluted with 20 mL of AcOEt and transferred to a separatory funnel where it was washed three times with 30 mL of brine. The organic extracts were combined, dried over Na_2SO_4 , filtered and concentrated *in vacuo* using a rotatory evaporator. The crude reaction mixture was analyzed by 1H -NMR and purified by flash column chromatography on silica gel.

6 Flow experiment

6.1 General procedure 2 (GP2): radical fluorooalkylation in continuous flow

To an oven-dried vial equipped with a stirring bar were added the α -fluoro acid (0.3 mmol, 1.3 equiv.) and potassium hydroxide (0.3 mmol, 1.3 equiv.). Upon complete solubilization, 4CzIPN (5.9 mg, 2.5 mol%), the SOMOphile (0.23 mmol, 1 equiv.) and dry DMSO (1 mL) were added. Subsequently, the vial was sealed with a rubber septum and the solution was sparged with N_2 (1 min). The solution was loaded in a 1 mL PTFE loop connected to a coil reactor (8 mL) contained in a PhotoCube™ photo-flow reactor equipped with a blue lamp ($\lambda = 457$ nm, 128 W). The solution was pumped (0.04 mL/min) through the coil employing a syringe pump equipped with a gastight syringe containing dry DMSO (10 mL). The reaction mixture was collected after 180 minutes from the start for 23 minutes. The solution was diluted with 20 mL of AcOEt and transferred to a separatory funnel where it was washed three times with 30 mL of brine. The organic extracts were combined, dried over Na_2SO_4 , filtered and concentrated *in vacuo* using a

rotatory evaporator. The crude reaction mixture was analyzed by $^1\text{H-NMR}$ and purified by flash column chromatography on silica gel.

6.2 General procedure 3 (GP3): radical-polar crossover in continuous flow

To an oven-dried vial equipped with a stirring bar were added 1-(tert-butoxycarbonyl)-4-fluoropiperidine-4-carboxylic acid (0.3 mmol, 1.3 equiv.) and potassium hydroxide (0.3 mmol, 1.3 equiv.). Upon complete solubilization, 4CzIPN (5.9 mg, 2.5 mol%), methyl acrylate (0.23 mmol, 1 equiv.), the appropriate aldehyde (0.69 mmol, 3 equiv.) and dry DMSO (1 mL) were added. Subsequently, the vial was sealed with a rubber septum and the solution was sparged with N_2 (1 min). The solution was loaded in a 1 mL PTFE loop connected to a coil reactor (8 mL) contained in a PhotoCube™ photo-flow reactor equipped with a blue lamp ($\lambda = 457 \text{ nm}$, 128 W). The solution was pumped (0.04 mL/min through the coil employing a syringe pump equipped with a gastight syringe containing dry DMSO (10 mL). The reaction mixture was collected after 180 minutes from the start for 23 minutes. The solution was diluted with 20 mL of AcOEt and transferred to a separatory funnel where it was washed three times with 30 mL of brine. The organic extracts were combined, dried over Na_2SO_4 , filtered and concentrated *in vacuo* using a rotatory evaporator. The crude reaction mixture was analyzed by $^1\text{H-NMR}$ and purified by flash column chromatography on silica gel.

6.3 Space Time Yields Calculation

- Batch
- Flow
- Gram scale

$$STY = \frac{\text{Mass of product}}{\text{Reaction Time} \cdot \text{Reactor volume}}$$

a) ● Batch: 3h
● Flow: 1.5h

b) ● Batch: 16h
● Flow: 3.5h

c) ● Batch: 3h
● Flow: 3h

Figure 4 Space time yield comparisons.

7 Substrate scope

methyl 4-fluoro-5-phenylpentanoate (5a)

Prepared following **GP2** with 2-fluoro-3-phenylpropanoic acid **1a** and methyl acrylate **S1a** as starting materials, compound **5a** was isolated as a colorless oil (44.0 mg, 0.21 mmol, 91%) by flash column chromatography $R_f = 0.4$ hexane/diethyl ether 9:1 (v/v).

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.38 – 7.22 (m, 5H), 4.85 – 4.64 (m, 1H), 3.70 (s, 3H), 3.08 – 2.84 (m, 2H), 2.61 – 2.42 (m, 2H), 2.08 – 1.90 (m, 2H).

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 173.5, 136.8 (d, $J = 4.9$ Hz), 129.4, 128.5, 126.7, 93.4 (d, $J = 171.8$ Hz), 51.7, 41.6 (d, $J = 21.3$ Hz), 29.9 (d, $J = 21.1$ Hz), 29.7 (d, $J = 4.1$ Hz).

^{19}F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -181.42 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/ cm^{-1} 3029, 2952, 2923, 1735, 1454, 1437, 1259, 1170, 745, 699.

HRMS calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{15}\text{FO}_2\text{Na}$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 233.0954; found 233.0950.

Benzyl 4-fluoro-2-methyl-5-phenylpentanoate (7)

Prepared following **GP2** with 2-fluoro-3-phenylpropanoic acid **1a** and benzyl methacrylate **S2a** as starting materials, compound **7** was obtained as a yellow oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr = 50:50). Compound **7** was isolated as a colorless oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr = 60:40, 55.2 mg, 0.18 mmol, 80%) after flash column chromatography (SiO_2) ($R_f = 0.3$, 9:1 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.40 – 7.16 (m, 16.6H), 5.16 – 5.11 (m, 3.3 H), 4.88 – 4.64 (m, 1.7 H), 3.08 – 2.72 (m, 4.9H), 2.24 – 1.92 (m, 1.8H), 1.81 – 1.60 (m, 1.7H), 1.26 – 1.21 (m, 5.1H).

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 176.0, 175.8, 136.9, 136.86 (d, $J = 4.6$ Hz), 136.84 (d, $J = 4.4$ Hz), 136.06, 136.05, 129.4, 128.54, 128.48, 128.43, 128.17, 128.11, 128.07, 126.7, 126.6, 92.6 (d, $J = 174.3$ Hz), 92.2 (d, $J = 172.0$ Hz), 66.32, 66.26, 41.9 (d, $J = 21.3$ Hz), 41.8 (d, $J = 21.3$ Hz), 38.8 (d, $J = 20.7$ Hz), 38.2 (d, $J = 20.8$ Hz), 36.1 (d, $J = 3.4$ Hz), 36.0 (d, $J = 2.7$ Hz), 18.0, 16.7.

^{19}F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -179.91 – -180.38 (m, 1F), -180.57 – -181.04 (m, 0.7F).

IR (film)/ cm^{-1} 2916, 2848, 1731, 1496, 1454, 1165, 1132, 909, 733, 698.

HRMS calcd for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{21}\text{FO}_2\text{Na}$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 323.1423; found 323.1437.

Ethyl 4-fluoro-2-methyl-5-phenylpentanoate (8)

Prepared following **GP2** with 2-fluoro-3-phenylpropanoic acid **1a** and Ethyl methacrylate **S2b** as starting materials, compound **8** was obtained as a yellow oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr = 45:55). Compound **8** was isolated as a colorless oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr = 75:25, 49.3 mg, 0.21 mmol, 90%) after flash column chromatography (SiO_2) ($R_f = 0.2$, 9:1 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.36 – 7.23 (m, 6.6H), 4.87 – 4.66 (m, 1.3H), 4.19 – 4.11 (m, 2.6H), 3.07 – 2.83 (m, 2.6H), 2.80 – 2.73 (m, 0.3H), 2.73 – 2.63 (m, 1H), 2.14 (m, 1H), 1.99 (m, 0.3H), 1.77 – 1.58 (m, 2.6H), 1.27 (t, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 3.9H), 1.21 (m, 3.9H).

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 176.3, 176.1, 136.9 (d, $J = 4.8$ Hz), 129.3, 128.5, 128.4, 126.7, 126.6, 92.7 (d, $J = 170.8$ Hz), 92.3 (d, $J = 171.9$ Hz), 60.5, 60.4, 41.9 (d, $J = 21.2$ Hz), 41.8 (d, $J = 21.3$ Hz), 38.7 (d, $J = 20.6$ Hz), 38.3 (d, $J = 20.7$ Hz), 36.0 (d, $J = 3.4$ Hz), 35.9 (d, $J = 2.7$ Hz), 18.1, 16.7, 14.2.

^{19}F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -179.98 – -180.39 (m, 1F), -180.64 – -181.05 (m, 0.3F).

IR (film)/ cm^{-1} 3029, 2931, 1730, 1602, 1454, 1375, 1259, 1176, 746, 699.

HRMS calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{19}\text{FO}_2\text{Na}$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 261.1267; found 261.1267.

2-hydroxyethyl 4-fluoro-2-methyl-5-phenylpentanoate (**9**)

Prepared following **GP2** with 2-fluoro-3-phenylpropanoic acid **1a** and 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate **S2c** as starting materials, compound **9** was obtained as a yellow oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr = 50:50). Compound **9** was isolated as a colorless oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr = 55:45, 50.3 mg, 0.20 mmol, 86%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.3, 8:2 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.36 – 7.21 (m, 9.1H), 4.90 – 4.69 (m, 1.8H), 4.29 – 4.17 (m, 3.6H), 3.84 – 3.78 (m, 3.6H), 3.09 – 2.68 (m, 5.4H), 2.22 – 1.90 (m, 1.8H), 1.84 – 1.59 (m, 1.8H), 1.23 (dd, J = 7.1, 5.8 Hz, 5.4H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 176.6, 176.4, 136.7 (d, J = 4.6 Hz), 136.3 (d, J = 4.8 Hz), 129.4, 128.5, 128.5, 126.8, 126.7, 92.8 (d, J = 171.5 Hz), 92.7 (d, J = 170.7 Hz), 66.2, 66.1, 61.2, 61.2, 41.8 (d, J = 21.3 Hz), 41.8 (d, J = 21.3 Hz), 38.6 (d, J = 18.1 Hz), 38.4 (d, J = 18.3 Hz), 36.4 (d, J = 2.9 Hz), 35.8 (d, J = 2.7 Hz), 17.9, 17.0.

¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -179.87 (m, 1F), -180.41 – -180.83 (m, 0.8F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 3430, 3029, 2933, 1730, 1600, 1454, 1375, 1259, 1176, 746.

HRMS calcd for C₁₄H₁₉FO₃Na [M+Na]⁺ 277.1216; found 277.1231.

methyl 4-fluoro-2,5-diphenylpentanoate (**10**)

Prepared following **GP2** with 2-fluoro-3-phenylpropanoic acid **1a** and methyl 2-phenylacrylate **S3b** as starting materials, compound **10** was obtained as a yellow oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr = 50:50). Compound **10** was isolated as a colorless oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr = 50:50, 58.6 mg, 0.20 mmol, 89%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.3, 9:1 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.38 – 7.15 (m, 20H), 4.89 – 4.70 (m, 1H), 4.56 – 4.37 (m, 1H), 3.91 (m, 2H), 3.68 (s, 6H), 3.04 – 2.80 (m, 4H), 2.57 – 2.36 (m, 2H), 2.22 – 1.94 (m, 2H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 174.1, 173.8, 138.9, 137.8, 136.8 (d, J = 3.9 Hz), 136.7 (d, J = 4.5 Hz), 129.4, 129.4, 128.8, 128.8, 128.5, 128.5, 128.2, 127.7, 127.6, 127.5, 126.7, 126.7, 92.5 (d, J = 171.2 Hz), 91.7 (d, J = 171.7 Hz), 52.17, 52.16, 47.5 (d, J = 2.8 Hz), 47.1 (d, J = 3.7 Hz), 41.8 (d, J = 6.1 Hz), 41.6 (d, J = 6.1 Hz), 39.0 (d, J = 20.7 Hz), 38.1 (d, J = 20.4 Hz).

¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -181.78 – -182.46 (m, 2F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 3030, 2931, 1730, 1600, 1454, 1375, 1259, 1176, 746, 699.

HRMS calcd for C₁₈H₁₉FO₂Na [M+Na]⁺ 309.1267; found 309.1270.

butyl 4-fluoro-5-phenylpentanoate (**11**)

Prepared following **GP2** with 2-fluoro-3-phenylpropanoic acid **1b** and Butyl acrylate **S1c** as starting materials, compound **11** was obtained as a yellow oil. Compound **11** was isolated as a colorless oil, (48.1 mg, 0.19 mmol, 83%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.2, 9:1 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.36 – 7.23 (m, 5H), 4.85 – 4.65 (m, 1), 4.10 (t, J = 6.7 Hz, 2H), 3.09 – 2.84 (m, 2H), 2.60 – 2.41 (m, 2H), 2.05 – 1.90 (m, 2H), 1.68 – 1.58 (m, 2H), 1.40 (m, 2H), 0.95 (t, J = 7.4 Hz, 3H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 173.1, 136.8 (d, J = 4.9 Hz), 129.4, 128.5, 126.7, 93.5 (d, J = 171.8 Hz), 64.5, 41.6 (d, J = 21.3 Hz), 30.6, 29.92 (d, J = 4.0 Hz), 29.91 (d, J = 21.0 Hz), 19.1, 13.7.

¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -180.28 – -181.93 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 3029, 2958, 2926, 2872, 1733, 1454, 1258, 1175, 745, 699.

HRMS calcd for C₁₄H₁₉FO₂Na [M+Na]⁺ 275.1423; found 275.1418.

ethyl 4-fluoro-6-phenylhexanoate (**12**)

Prepared following **GP2** with 2-fluoro-4-phenylbutanoic acid **1b** and Ethyl acrylate **S1b** as starting materials, compound **12** was obtained as a yellow oil. Compound **12** was isolated as a colorless oil, (41.8 mg, 0.17 mmol, 75%) after flash column chromatography (SiO_2) ($R_f = 0.3$, 9:1 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.34 – 7.20 (m, 5H), 4.64 – 4.45 (m, 1H), 4.16 (q, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 2H), 2.89 – 2.68 (m, 2H), 2.57 – 2.40 (m, 2H), 2.09 – 1.89 (m, 4H), 1.27 (t, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 3H).

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 173.1, 141.3, 128.5, 128.4, 126.0, 92.5 (d, $J = 168.7$ Hz), 60.5, 36.9 (d, $J = 20.8$ Hz), 31.3 (d, $J = 4.5$ Hz), 30.3 (d, $J = 21.1$ Hz), 29.9 (d, $J = 4.2$ Hz), 14.2.

$^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -184.21 – -184.64 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/ cm^{-1} 3027, 2932, 1731, 1454, 1374, 1248, 1178, 1029, 746, 698.

HRMS calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{19}\text{FO}_2\text{Na}$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 261.1267; found 261.1275 .

ethyl 4-fluoro-6-phenylhexanoate (**13**)

Prepared following **GP2** with 2-fluoro-4-phenylbutanoic acid **1b** and Hexyl acrylate **S1d** as starting materials, compound **13** was obtained as a yellow oil. Compound **13** was isolated as a colorless oil, (47.7 mg, 0.16 mmol, 70%) after flash column chromatography (SiO_2) ($R_f = 0.5$, 9:1 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.35 – 7.19 (m, 5H), 4.65 – 4.45 (m, 1H), 4.09 (t, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 2H), 2.89 – 2.68 (m, 2H), 2.57 – 2.41 (m, 2H), 2.09 – 1.89 (m, 4H), 1.67 – 1.61 (m, 2H), 1.41 – 1.27 (m, 6H), 0.95 – 0.89 (m, 3H).

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 173.2, 141.3, 128.5, 128.4, 126.0, 92.5 (d, $J = 168.8$ Hz), 64.7, 36.9 (d, $J = 20.9$ Hz), 31.4, 31.3 (d, $J = 4.5$ Hz), 30.4 (d, $J = 21.1$ Hz), 29.9 (d, $J = 4.2$ Hz), 28.6, 25.6, 22.5, 14.0.

$^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (377 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -184.13 – -184.66 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/ cm^{-1} 3027, 2954, 2929, 2858, 1735, 1454, 1176, 1046, 909, 699.

HRMS calcd for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{27}\text{FO}_2\text{Na}$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 317.1893; found 317,1900.

benzyl 4-fluoro-2-methyl-6-phenylhexanoate (**14**)

Prepared following **GP2** with 2-fluoro-4-phenylbutanoic acid **1b** and benzyl methacrylate **S2a** as starting materials, compound **14** was obtained as a yellow oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr = 50:50, 75%). Compound **14** was isolated as a colorless oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr = 99:1, 27.1 mg, 0.09 mmol, 37.5%) after flash column chromatography (SiO_2) ($R_f = 0.3$, 9:1 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.42 – 7.29 (m, 7H), 7.25 – 7.18 (m, 3H), 5.15 (d, $J = 3.4$ Hz, 2H), 4.64 – 4.43 (m, 1H), 2.81 (m, 2H), 2.67 (m, 1H), 2.07 – 1.70 (m, 4H), 1.25 (d, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 3H).

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 176.0, 141.3, 136.0, 128.6, 128.5, 128.4, 128.2, 128.1, 126.0, 91.9 (d, $J = 168.1$ Hz), 66.3, 39.2 (d, $J = 20.8$ Hz), 37.3 (d, $J = 20.8$ Hz), 36.0 (d, $J = 2.9$ Hz), 31.3 (d, $J = 4.6$ Hz), 18.0.

$^{19}\text{F NMR}$ (376 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -183.22 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/ cm^{-1} 3028, 2923, 2851, 1732, 1496, 1454, 1167, 1134, 747, 697.

HRMS calcd for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{23}\text{FO}_2\text{Na}$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 337.1580; found 337.1577.

tert-butyl 4-(3-ethoxy-3-oxopropyl)-4-fluoropiperidine-1-carboxylate (**15**)

Prepared following **GP2** with 1-(tert-butoxycarbonyl)-4-fluoropiperidine-4-carboxylic acid **1c** and ethyl acrylate **S1b** as starting materials, compound **15** was obtained as a yellow oil. Compound **15** was isolated as a colorless oil (62.8 mg, 0.21 mmol, 90%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.4, 8:1 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 4.16 (q, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 2H), 4.01 – 3.89 (m, 2H), 3.14 – 3.03 (m, 2H), 2.49 – 2.43 (m, 2H), 2.02 – 1.92 (m, 2H), 1.87 – 1.76 (m, 2H), 1.67 – 1.50 (m, 2H), 1.48 (s, 9H), 1.28 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 3H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 173.2, 154.7, 93.2 (d, *J* = 172.6 Hz), 79.7, 60.6, 39.5, 34.98 (d, *J* = 22.3 Hz), 34.4 (d, *J* = 21.2 Hz), 28.4, 27.9 (d, *J* = 4.2 Hz), 14.2.

¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -164.93 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 2976, 1734, 1691, 1419, 1365, 1244, 1151, 1025, 863, 769.

HRMS calcd for C₁₅H₂₆FNO₄Na [M+Na]⁺ 326.1744; found 326.1739.

tert-butyl 4-fluoro-4-(3-methoxy-3-oxo-1-phenylpropyl)piperidine-1-carboxylate (**16**)

Prepared following **GP2** with 1-(tert-butoxycarbonyl)-4-fluoropiperidine-4-carboxylic acid **1c** and methyl cinnamate **S3b** as starting materials, compound **16** was obtained as a brown oil. Compound **16** was isolated as a colorless oil (67.2 mg, 0.18 mmol, 80%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.3, 9:1 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.33 – 7.14 (m, 5H), 4.06 (m, 2H), 3.56 (s, 3H), 3.09 – 3.03 (m, 2H), 3.01 – 2.95 (m, 1H), 2.08 – 1.83 (m, 4H), 1.74 – 1.55 (m, 2H), 1.49 (s, 9H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 172.0, 154.6, 138.6, 128.7, 128.6, 126.6, 93.8 (d, *J* = 178.4 Hz), 79.7, 57.5 (d, *J* = 23.4 Hz), 51.7, 39.3, 33.3 (d, *J* = 21.7 Hz), 32.9 (d, *J* = 4.5 Hz), 31.9 (d, *J* = 21.7 Hz), 28.4.

¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -162.94 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 2926, 1734, 1691, 1421, 1364, 1242, 1146, 1126, 748, 699.

HRMS calcd for C₂₀H₂₈FNO₄Na [M+Na]⁺ 388.1900; found 388.1903

2-(3-fluoro-4-phenylbutyl)pyridine (**17**)

Prepared following **GP2** with 2-fluoro-3-phenylpropanoic acid **1a** and 2-vinylpyridine **S6** as starting materials, compound **17** was obtained as a brown oil. Compound **17** was isolated as a colorless oil (42.1 mg, 0.18 mmol, 80%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.2, 7:3 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.56 (dd, *J* = 5.0, 0.9 Hz, 1H), 7.65 (td, *J* = 7.7, 1.8 Hz, 1H), 7.35 – 7.15 (m, 7H), 4.85 – 4.66 (m, 1H), 3.12 – 2.87 (m, 4H), 2.22 – 2.05 (m, 2H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 160.7, 148.5, 137.13, 137.08, 129.4, 128.4, 126.6, 123.4, 121.5, 93.8 (d, *J* = 171.7 Hz), 41.7 (d, *J* = 21.3 Hz), 34.5 (d, *J* = 20.8 Hz), 33.4.

¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -180.15 – -180.57 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 3018, 2922, 2855, 1628, 1379, 1262, 1085, 1031, 860, 789.

HRMS calcd for C₁₅H₁₆FNNa [M+Na]⁺ 252.1164; found 252.1155.

4-(3-fluoro-4-phenylbutyl)pyridine (18)

Prepared following **GP2** with 2-fluoro-3-phenylpropanoic acid **1a** and 4-vinylpyridine **S5** as starting materials, compound **18** was obtained as a brown oil. Compound **18** was isolated as a colorless oil (41.1 mg, 0.18 mmol, 78%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.3, 7:3 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.52 – 8.50 (m, 2H), 7.36 – 7.19 (m, 5H), 7.14 – 7.10 (m, 2H), 4.80 – 4.60 (m, 1H), 3.10 – 2.67 (m, 4H), 2.08 – 1.80 (m, 2H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 150.4, 149.7, 136.7 (d, *J* = 5.2 Hz), 129.3, 128.5, 126.8, 123.9, 93.2 (d, *J* = 172.3 Hz), 41.6 (d, *J* = 21.4 Hz), 35.2 (d, *J* = 21.1 Hz), 30.7 (d, *J* = 4.1 Hz).

¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -180.07 – -180.52 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 3028, 2924, 2855, 1630, 1379, 1260, 1085, 1031, 863, 799.

HRMS calcd for C₁₅H₁₇FN [M+H]⁺ 230.1345; found 230.1333.

1-chloro-4-(3-fluoro-4-phenylbutyl)benzene (19)

Prepared following **GP2** with 2-fluoro-3-phenylpropanoic acid **1a** and 1-chloro-4-vinylbenzene **S8a** as starting materials, compound **19** was obtained as a yellow oil. Compound **19** was isolated as a colorless oil (36.2 mg, 0.14 mmol, 60%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.3, 9:1 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.36 – 7.10 (m, 9H), 4.80 – 4.60 (m, 1H), 3.08 – 2.80 (m, 3H), 2.69 (m, 1H), 2.04 – 1.77 (m, 2H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 139.8, 137.0 (d, *J* = 4.9 Hz), 131.7, 129.8, 129.4, 128.5, 128.5, 126.7, 93.4 (d, *J* = 171.8 Hz), 41.6 (d, *J* = 21.3 Hz), 36.3 (d, *J* = 21.1 Hz), 30.7 (d, *J* = 4.2 Hz).

¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -180.34 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 3028, 2924, 2855, 1492, 1454, 1091, 1014, 831, 744, 699.

HRMS calcd for C₁₆H₁₅ClF [M-H]⁺ 261.0841; found 261.0849.

tert-butyl 4-fluoro-4-(2-(perfluorophenyl)ethyl)piperidine-1-carboxylate (20)

Prepared following **GP2** with 1-(tert-butoxycarbonyl)-4-fluoropiperidine-4-carboxylic acid **1a** and 1,2,3,4,5-pentafluoro-6-vinylbenzene **S7** as starting materials, compound **20** was isolated as a colorless oil (63.9 mg, 0.16 mmol, 70%) by flash column chromatography (R_f = 0.4, 9:1 hexane/diethyl ether).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 4.06 – 3.91 (m, 2H), 3.18 – 3.05 (m, 2H), 2.89 – 2.81 (m, 2H), 1.96 – 1.81 (m, 2H), 1.67 – 1.52 (m, 2H), 1.48 (s, 9H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 154.6, 146.6 – 145.8 (m), 144.1 – 143.4 (m), 141.3 – 140.7 (m), 139.2 – 138.2 (m), 136.9 – 135.8 (m), 115.0 – 114.2 (m), 93.2 (d, *J* = 173.2 Hz), 79.7, 39.6, 39.3 (d, *J* = 22.2 Hz), 34.5, 34.3 (d, *J* = 21.7 Hz), 30.9, 28.4, 16.0.

¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -144.48 – -144.56 (m, 2F), -157.46 – -157.57 (m, 1F), -162.56 – -162.74 (m, 2F), -165.28 – -165.53 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 2961, 1690, 1519, 1501, 1421, 1366, 1246, 1153, 951, 731.

HRMS calcd for C₁₈H₂₁F₆NO₂Na [M+Na]⁺ 420.1374; found 420.1386.

2-(3-fluoro-4-methyloctyl)pyridine (21)

Prepared following **GP2** with 2-fluorooctanoic acid **1d** and 2-vinylpyridine **S6** as starting materials, compound **21** was obtained as a yellow oil. Compound **21** was isolated as a colorless oil (47.0 mg, 0.15 mmol, 65%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.6, 6:4 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.58 – 8.55 (m, 1H), 7.65 – 7.59 (m, 1H), 7.21 – 7.11 (m, 2H), 4.63 – 4.43 (m, 1H), 3.06 – 2.84 (m, 2H), 2.15 – 1.99 (m, 2H), 1.77 – 1.51 (m, 4H), 1.35 – 1.26 (m, 8H), 0.90 (t, J = 6.7 Hz, 3H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 161.3, 149.3, 136.4, 123.0, 121.1, 93.9 (d, J = 167.6 Hz), 35.2 (d, J = 20.6 Hz), 35.0 (d, J = 21.0 Hz), 33.9 (d, J = 4.2 Hz), 31.9, 29.5, 29.2, 25.1 (d, J = 4.6 Hz), 22.7, 14.1.

¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -181.35 – -181.76 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 2923, 2854, 1590, 1569, 1473, 1434, 1258, 1049, 776, 748.

HRMS not found in ESI+ or ESI-mode.

(1,1,4-trifluorodec-1-en-2-yl)benzene (22)

Prepared following **GP2** with 2-fluorooctanoic acid **1d** and (3,3,3-trifluoroprop-1-en-2-yl)benzene **S4** as starting materials, compound **15** was obtained as a yellow oil. Compound **15** was isolated as a colorless oil (42.5 mg, 0.15 mmol, 65%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.4, hexane).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.43 – 7.30 (m, 5H), 4.45 (m, 1H), 2.85 – 2.55 (m, 2H), 1.70 – 1.41 (m, 4H), 1.35 – 1.24 (m, 8H), 0.90 (t, J = 6.9 Hz, 3H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 154.4 (dd, J = 290.5 Hz, 288.3 Hz), 133.3 – 133.2 (m), 128.5, 128.4 (t, J = 3.2 Hz), 127.5, 91.9 (dt, J = 171.0, 2.9 Hz), 89.2 – 88.8 (m), 34.8 (d, J = 20.6 Hz), 33.9 (dd, J = 23.5, 1.8 Hz), 31.8, 29.4 (d, J = 3.3 Hz), 29.2, 24.9 (d, J = 4.2 Hz), 22.7, 14.1.

¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -89.84 – -89.97 (m, 1F), -90.20 (m, 1F), -180.27 (ddt, J = 64.5, 29.9, 15.0 Hz, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 2925, 2855, 1731, 1446, 1306, 1242, 1127, 1070, 769, 696.

HRMS not found in ESI+ or ESI-mode.

tert-butyl 3-fluoro-3-(2-(perfluorophenyl)ethyl)azetidine-1-carboxylate (23)

Prepared following **GP2** with 1-(tert-butoxycarbonyl)-3-fluoroazetidine-3-carboxylic acid **1e** and 1,2,3,4,5-pentafluoro-6-vinylbenzene **S7** as starting materials, compound **23** was obtained as a brown oil. Compound **23** was isolated as a colorless oil (28.9 mg, 0.08 mmol, 34%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.3, 8:2 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 4.16 – 4.06 (m, 2H), 3.97 – 3.89 (m, 2H), 2.90 – 2.81 (m, 2H), 2.23 – 2.11 (m, 2H), 1.48 (s, 9H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 156.1, 146.2, 145.7, 145.3, 143.8, 143.3, 141.2, 140.5, 138.8, 136.7, 136.2, 113.8, 113.7, 91.2 (d, J = 208.1 Hz), 80.3, 59.7, 35.4 (d, J = 22.9 Hz), 31.6, 28.3.

¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -144.28 – -144.43 (m, 2F), -152.83 – -153.15 (m, 1F), -156.70 – -156.89 (m, 1F), -162.23 – -162.40 (m, 2F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 2978, 1690, 1519, 1501, 1420, 1366, 1246, 1153, 951, 731.

HRMS calcd for C₁₆H₁₇F₆NO₂Na [M+Na]⁺ 392.1691; found 392.1054.

tert-butyl 3-fluoro-3-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenethyl)azetidone-1-carboxylate (24)

Prepared following **GP2** with 1-(*tert*-butoxycarbonyl)-3-fluoroazetidone-3-carboxylic acid **1e** and 1-(trifluoromethyl)-4-vinylbenzene **S8b** as starting materials, compound **23** was obtained as a brown oil. Compound **23** was isolated as a colorless oil (14.0 mg, 0.04 mmol, 17%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.2, 8:2 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.58 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 2H), 7.34 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 2H), 4.08 (m, 2H), 3.87 (m, 2H), 2.87 – 2.77 (m, 2H), 2.28 – 2.14 (m, 2H), 1.47 (s, 9H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 156.2, 144.7, 128.7, 125.5 (q, *J* = 3.8 Hz), 91.4 (d, *J* = 207.2 Hz), 80.1, 59.9, 59.6, 37.76 (d, *J* = 23.5 Hz), 29.1 (d, *J* = 3.8 Hz), 28.3.

¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -62.45 (m, 3F), -152.07 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 2978, 1704, 1618, 1405, 1325, 1163, 1123, 1018, 846, 749.

HRMS calcd for C₁₇H₂₁F₄NO₂Na [M+Na]⁺ 370.1406; found 370.1420.

4-fluoro-N,N-dimethyl-5-phenylpentanamide (25)

Prepared following **GP2** with 2-fluoro-3-phenylpropanoic acid **1a** and N,N-dimethylacrylamide **S9** as starting materials, compound **25** was obtained as a yellow oil. Compound **25** was isolated as a colorless oil (20.5 mg, 0.09 mmol, 40%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.3, 6:4 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.35 – 7.22 (m, 5H), 4.89 – 4.68 (m, 1H), 3.06 – 2.90 (m, 8H), 2.57 – 2.41 (m, 2H), 2.17 – 1.84 (m, 2H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 172.1, 137.0 (d, *J* = 4.5 Hz), 129.4, 128.4, 126.6, 94.0 (d, *J* = 170.6 Hz), 41.8 (d, *J* = 21.2 Hz), 37.1, 35.4, 30.2 (d, *J* = 20.3 Hz), 28.6 (d, *J* = 3.3 Hz).

¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -181.35 – -181.81 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 3028, 2960, 2918, 2856, 1652, 1476, 1375, 1074, 767, 699.

HRMS calcd for C₁₃H₁₈FNONa [M+Na]⁺ 246.1270; found 246.1264.

tert-butyl 4-fluoro-4-(3-oxocyclohexyl)piperidine-1-carboxylate (26)

Prepared following **GP2** with 1-(*tert*-butoxycarbonyl)-4-fluoropiperidine-4-carboxylic acid **1c** and cyclohex-2-en-1-one **S10** as starting materials, compound **26** was isolated as a colorless oil (48.2 mg, 0.16 mmol, 70%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.5, 6:4 hexane/ diethyl ether).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 4.09 – 3.93 (m, 2H), 3.11 – 2.96 (m, 2H), 2.56 – 2.38 (m, 2H), 2.34 – 2.11 (m, 3H), 2.05 – 1.95 (m, 1H), 1.95 – 1.76 (m, 3H), 1.70 – 1.50 (m, 4H), 1.48 (s, 9H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 210.8, 154.7, 94.7 (d, *J* = 175.6 Hz), 79.7, 46.9 (d, *J* = 22.0 Hz), 41.9 (d, *J* = 4.7 Hz), 41.2, 39.4, 32.1 (d, *J* = 22.7 Hz), 28.4, 24.90, 24.86.

¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -170.08 – -171.80 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 2962, 2869, 1686, 1421, 1365, 1242, 1150, 913, 863, 729, 646.

HRMS calcd for C₁₆H₂₆FNO₃Na [M+Na]⁺ 322.1794; found 322.1826.

tert-butyl 4-fluoro-4-(2-(phenylsulfinyl)ethyl)piperidine-1-carboxylate (**27**)

Prepared following **GP2** with 1-(tert-butoxycarbonyl)-4-fluoropiperidine-4-carboxylic acid **1c** and (vinylsulfinyl)benzene **S11** as starting materials, compound **27** was isolated as a colorless oil (42.0 mg, 0.12 mmol, 51%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.4, 5:5 hexane/ diethyl ether).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.65 – 7.50 (m, 5H), 4.01 – 3.83 (m, 2H), 3.12 – 2.97 (m, 3H), 2.85 (ddd, *J* = 13.1, 11.6, 4.9 Hz, 1H), 2.17 – 2.01 (m, 1H), 1.93 – 1.72 (m, 3H), 1.68 – 1.51 (m, 2H), 1.46 (s, 9H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 154.6, 143.3, 131.2, 129.3, 124.0, 93.0 (d, *J* = 173.8 Hz), 79.8, 50.3, 34.73–34.32 (m), 32.0 (d, *J* = 22.7 Hz), 29.7, 28.4.

¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -163.77 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 2971, 2927, 1690, 1422, 1365, 1243, 1152, 1045, 862, 748, 692.

HRMS calcd for C₁₈H₂₆FNO₃SNa [M+Na]⁺ 378.1515; found 378.1550.

tert-butyl 4-fluoro-4-(2-(phenylsulfonyl)ethyl)piperidine-1-carboxylate (**28**)

Prepared following **GP2** with 1-(tert-butoxycarbonyl)-4-fluoropiperidine-4-carboxylic acid **1c** and (vinylsulfonyl)benzene **S12** as starting materials, compound **28** was isolated as a colorless oil (46.9 mg, 0.13 mmol, 55%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.4, 5:5 hexane/ diethyl ether).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.96 – 7.92 (m, 2H), 7.74 – 7.58 (m, 3H), 4.01 – 3.87 (m, 2H), 3.29 – 3.19 (m, 2H), 3.09 – 2.98 (m, 2H), 2.12 – 1.98 (m, 2H), 1.83 – 1.71 (m, 2H), 1.65 – 1.51 (m, 2H), 1.46 (s, 9H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 154.6, 138.9, 134.0, 129.4, 128.0, 92.4 (d, *J* = 174.8 Hz), 79.9, 50.5 (d, *J* = 4.1 Hz), 39.4, 34.4 (d, *J* = 21.5 Hz), 32.7 (d, *J* = 22.5 Hz), 29.7.

¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -164.47 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 2960, 2920, 1686, 1446, 1421, 1304, 1146, 1085, 742, 689, 536.

HRMS calcd for C₁₈H₂₆FNO₄SNa [M+Na]⁺ 394.1464; found 394.1503.

(4*R**,1*S**,2*R**,5*S**)/(4*S**,1*S**,2*R**,5*S**)-2'-isopropyl-5'-methylcyclohexyl 4-fluoro-5-phenylpentanoate (**29**)

Prepared following **GP2** with 2-fluoro-3-phenylpropanoic acid **1a** and 2-isopropyl-5-methylcyclohexyl acrylate **S13** as starting materials, compound **29** was obtained as a yellow oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr > 20:1). Compound **29** was isolated as a colorless oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr > 20:1, 70.7 mg, 0.21 mmol, 92%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.3, hexane).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.36 – 7.22 (m, 5H), 4.84 – 4.64 (m, 2H), 3.08 – 2.84 (m, 2H), 2.58 – 2.39 (m, 2H), 2.05 – 1.81 (m, 4H), 1.70 (m, 2H), 1.50 (m, 1H), 1.3 (m, 2H), 1.14 – 0.95 (m, 2H), 0.93 – 0.89 (m, 6H), 0.76 (dd, *J* = 6.9, 1.5 Hz, 3H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 172.6, 136.9 (d, *J* = 4.8 Hz), 129.4, 128.5, 126.7, 93.5 (d, *J* = 171.8 Hz), 74.3, 47.0, 41.6 (d, *J* = 21.4 Hz), 40.9, 34.2, 31.4, 30.2 (d, *J* = 4.4 Hz), 30.0 (d, *J* = 21.0 Hz), 26.3, 23.4, 22.0, 20.7, 16.3.

¹⁹F NMR (377 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -180.89 – -181.47 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 2953, 2923, 2869, 1729, 1454, 1369, 1257, 1177, 745, 699.

HRMS calcd for C₂₁H₃₁FO₂Na [M+Na]⁺ 357.2206; found 357.2218.

tert-butyl 4-(3-(adamantan-1-ylamino)-3-oxopropyl)-4-fluoropiperidine-1-carboxylate (**30**)

Prepared following **GP2** with 1-(tert-butoxycarbonyl)-4-fluoropiperidine-4-carboxylic acid **1c** and N-(adamantan-1-yl)acrylamide **S15** as starting materials, compound **30** was obtained as a yellow oil. Compound **30** was isolated as a colorless oil (20.2 mg, 0.10 mmol, 42%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.3, 7:3 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 5.16 (br, 1H), 3.97 – 3.84 (m, 2H), 3.11 – 3.05 (m, 2H), 2.24 (m, 2H), 2.11 – 2.05 (m, 3H), 2.00 (m, 6H), 1.98 – 1.91 (m, 2H),

1.79 (m, 2H), 1.69 (m, 6H), 1.67 – 1.50 (m, 2H), 1.47 (s, 9H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 171.2, 154.7, 93.7 (d, *J* = 172.0 Hz), 79.6, 51.9, 41.6, 36.3, 35.5, 34.5 (d, *J* = 21.8 Hz), 30.7 (d, *J* = 3.6 Hz), 29.7, 29.4, 28.4.

¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -163.95 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 3320, 2907, 2850, 1685, 1650, 1542, 1422, 1365, 1153, 731.

HRMS calcd for C₂₃H₃₇FN₂O₃Na [M+Na]⁺ 431.2686; found 431.2674.

tert-butyl 4-(3-(4-((4-chlorophenyl)(pyridin-2-yl)methoxy)piperidin-1-yl)-3-oxopropyl)-4-fluoropiperidine-1-carboxylate (**31**)

Prepared following **GP2** with 1-(tert-butoxycarbonyl)-4-fluoropiperidine-4-carboxylic acid **1c** and 1-(4-((4-chlorophenyl)(pyridin-2-yl)methoxy)piperidin-1-yl)prop-2-en-1-one **S14** as starting materials, compound **31** was isolated as a colorless oil (47.6 mg, 0.08 mmol, 37%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.3, ethyl acetate).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.54 (d, *J* = 4.5 Hz, 1H), 7.71 (td, *J* = 7.7, 1.6 Hz, 1H), 7.53 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 7.39 (d, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 2H), 7.31 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.20 (dd, *J* = 6.8, 5.5 Hz, 1H), 5.64 (s, 1H), 4.01 – 3.84 (m, 3H), 3.78 – 3.65 (m, 2H), 3.44 – 3.33 (m, 1H), 3.32 – 3.23 (m, 1H), 3.09 (t, *J* = 12.1 Hz, 2H), 2.50 – 2.42 (m, 2H), 2.05 – 1.92 (m, 2H), 1.91 – 1.77 (m, 4H), 1.76 – 1.63 (m, 4H), 1.48 (s, 9H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 170.5, 161.7, 154.7, 149.0, 140.0, 139.9, 137.0, 133.5, 128.6, 128.1, 122.6, 120.6, 120.6, 93.6 (d, *J* = 172.0 Hz), 81.2, 79.6, 72.3 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz), 42.6, 42.5, 39.0, 35.2 (d, *J* = 21.5 Hz), 34.6 (d, *J* = 20.4 Hz), 31.7, 30.9, 30.9, 28.4.

¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -164.08 – -164.64 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 2924, 2856, 1626, 1589, 1501, 1434, 1366, 1265, 1085, 769.

HRMS calcd for C₃₀H₄₀ClFN₃O₄ [M+H]⁺ 560.2686; found 560.2682.

tert-butyl 4-fluoro-4-(3-(((8R,9S,13S,14S)-13-methyl-17-oxo-7,8,9,11,12,13,14,15,16,17-decahydro-6H-cyclopenta[a]phenanthren-3-yl)oxy)-3-oxopropyl)piperidine-1-carboxylate (32)

Prepared following **GP2** with 1-(tert-butoxycarbonyl)-4-fluoropiperidine-4-carboxylic acid **1c** and (8R,9S,13S,14S)-13-methyl-17-oxo-7,8,9,11,12,13,14,15,16,17-decahydro-6H-cyclopenta[a]phenanthrene-3-yl acrylate **S16** as starting materials, compound **32** was obtained as a yellow oil. Compound **32** was isolated as a colorless oil (75.2 mg, 0.14 mmol, 62%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.3, 8:2 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.30 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 1H), 6.87 (dd, *J* = 8.5, 2.3 Hz, 1H), 6.83 (s, 1H), 4.06 – 3.89 (m, 2H), 3.18 – 3.06 (m, 2H), 2.98 – 2.83 (m, 3H), 2.76 – 2.67 (m, 2H), 2.58 – 2.47 (m, 1H), 2.46 – 2.38 (m, 1H), 2.35 – 2.26 (m, 1H), 2.22 – 1.95 (m, 6H), 1.94 – 1.83 (m, 2H), 1.68 – 1.56 (m, 7H), 1.49 (s, 9H), 0.93 (s, 3H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) 220.6, 172.0, 154.7, 148.5, 138.0, 137.5, 126.4, 121.4, 118.6, 93.2 (d, *J* = 172.8 Hz), 79.7, 50.5, 47.9, 44.2, 44.0, 38.0, 35.8, 35.0 (d, *J* = 22.4 Hz), 34.5 (d, *J* = 21.6 Hz), 31.6, 29.7, 29.4, 28.4, 28.0 (d, *J* = 4.3 Hz), 26.3, 25.7, 21.6, 13.8.

¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -164.42 – -164.91 (m).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 2926, 1736, 1689, 1492, 1421, 1365, 1228, 1151, 909, 729.

HRMS calcd for C₃₁H₄₂FNO₅Na [M+Na]⁺ 550.2945; found 550.2939.

tert-butyl 4-(3-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-hydroxy-2-(methoxycarbonyl)propyl)-4-fluoropiperidine-1-carboxylate (33)

Prepared following **GP3** with 1-(tert-butoxycarbonyl)-4-fluoropiperidine-4-carboxylic acid **1c**, methyl acrylate **S1a** and 4-chlorobenzaldehyde **S17a** as starting materials.

Compound **33** was obtained as a yellow oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr = 50:50). Compound **33** was isolated as a colorless oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr = 60:40, 54.3 mg, 0.13 mmol, 55%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.3, 7:3 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.38 – 7.24 (m, 6.4H), 4.90 (d, *J* = 5.5 Hz, 1H), 4.76 (d, *J* = 3.2 Hz, 0.6H), 3.87 (m, 3.2H), 3.68 (s, 1.8H), 3.61 (s, 3H), 3.07 – 2.89 (m, 4.8H), 2.31 – 2.10 (m, 1.6H), 1.93 – 1.80 (m, 3.2H), 1.71 (m, 3.2H), 1.62 – 1.51 (m, 1.6H), 1.45 (s, 14.4H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 175.1, 175.0, 154.60, 154.57, 140.0, 139.5, 134.1, 133.7, 128.9, 128.6, 127.7, 127.5, 93.3 (d, *J* = 172.4 Hz), 93.1 (d, *J* = 172.9 Hz), 79.72, 79.69, 75.4, 73.6, 52.1, 52.1, 47.5, 47.3, 39.8 (d, *J* = 21.5 Hz), 39.6 – 39.4 (m), 37.3 (d, *J* = 21.3 Hz), 35.4 – 34.7 (m), 34.1 – 33.5 (m), 28.4.

¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -163.14 – -163.70 (m, 1.6F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 3432, 2954, 2924, 2853, 1735, 1692, 1670, 1432, 1366, 1156.

HRMS calcd for C₂₁H₂₉ClFNO₅Na [M+Na]⁺ 452.1616; found 452.1595.

tert-butyl 4-fluoro-4-(3-hydroxy-2-(methoxycarbonyl)-3-(pyridin-3-yl)propyl)piperidine-1-carboxylate (34)

Prepared following **GP3** with 1-(tert-butoxycarbonyl)-4-fluoropiperidine-4-carboxylic acid **1c**, methyl acrylate **S1a** and 4-chlorobenzaldehyde **S19** as starting materials.

Compound **34** was obtained as a yellow oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr = 50:50). Compound **34** was isolated as a colorless oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr = 50:50, 18.2 mg, 0.05 mmol, 20%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.2, ethyl acetate).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.61 – 8.53 (m, 4H), 7.76 – 7.68 (m, 2H), 7.36 – 7.26 (m, 2H), 5.01 – 4.94 (m, 1H), 4.87 – 4.81 (m, 1H), 3.97 – 3.84 (m, 4H), 3.68 (s, 3H), 3.68 (s, 3H), 3.11 – 2.96 (m, 6H), 2.38 – 2.18 (m, 4H), 1.93 – 1.83 (m, 4H), 1.76 – 1.63 (m, 4H), 1.46 (s, 9H), 1.45 (s, 9H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 174.9, 174.7, 155.1, 154.6, 149.7, 149.4, 148.2, 148.0, 137.06, 136.97, 133.9, 133.8, 123.6, 123.3, 93.3 (d, J = 172.5 Hz), 93.1 (d, J = 172.3 Hz), 79.73, 79.68, 73.8, 72.3, 52.2, 52.1, 47.3, 47.1, 39.9-38.9 (m), 39.7 (d, J = 21.3 Hz), 37.4 (d, J = 20.9 Hz), 34.3 – 33.6 (m), 28.4.

¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -163.10 – -163.79 (m, 2F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 3432, 2954, 2924, 2853, 1735, 1670, 1569, 1432, 1366, 1156.

HRMS not found in ESI+ or ESI-mode.

tert-butyl 4-fluoro-4-(3-hydroxy-2-(methoxycarbonyl)-3-(3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl) propyl) piperidine-1-carboxylate (35)

Prepared following **GP3** with 1-(tert-butoxycarbonyl)-4-fluoropiperidine-4-carboxylic acid **1c**, methyl acrylate **S1a** and 3-(trifluoromethyl)benzaldehyde **S18** as starting materials.

Compound **35** was obtained as a brown oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr = 50:50, 45%). Compound **35** was isolated as a colorless oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr = 99:1, 24.0 mg, 0.05 mmol, 23%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.5, 5:5 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.66 – 7.34 (m, 4H), 5.02 – 4.99 (m, 1H), 3.95 – 3.83 (m, 2H), 3.62 (s, 3H), 3.11 – 2.94 (m, 3H), 2.40 – 2.17 (m, 4H), 1.93 – 1.78 (m, 2H), 1.45 (s, 9H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 174.9, 154.6, 140.2, 130.89 (q, J = 32.4 Hz), 129.42, 128.93, 124.8 (m), 123.0 (m), 93.3 (d, J = 172.6 Hz), 79.7, 73.6, 52.1, 47.4, 39.4 (m), 37.1 (d, J = 21.3 Hz), 35.2, 33.9, 28.4.

¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -62.63 – -62.87 (m, 3F), -163.13 – -163.73 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 3431, 2920, 2849, 1734, 1669, 1436, 1328, 1162, 1124, 1073.

HRMS calcd for C₂₂H₂₉F₄NO₅Na [M+Na]⁺ 486.1880; found 486.1918.

tert-butyl 4-fluoro-4-(3-(4-fluorophenyl)-3-hydroxy-2-(methoxycarbonyl)propyl)piperidine-1-carboxylate (36)

Prepared following **GP3** with 1-(tert-butoxycarbonyl)-4-fluoropiperidine-4-carboxylic acid **1c**, methyl acrylate **S1a** and 3-(trifluoromethyl)benzaldehyde **S17b** as starting materials.

Compound **36** was obtained as a brown oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr = 50:50).

Compound **36-d1** was isolated as a colorless oil (36.1 mg, 0.09 mmol, 38%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.25, 7:3 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

d1-¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.37 – 7.31 (m, 2H), 7.10 – 7.02 (m, 2H), 4.90 (d, *J* = 5.7 Hz, 1H), 3.93 – 3.81 (m, 2H), 3.60 (s, 3H), 3.09 – 2.98 (m, 2H), 2.97 – 2.89 (m, 1H), 2.32 – 2.17 (m, 1H), 1.99 – 1.70 (m, 4H), 1.65 – 1.58 (m, 2H), 1.46 (s, 9H).

d1-¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 175.0, 162.4 (d, *J* = 246.4 Hz), 154.6, 136.7 (d, *J* = 3.1 Hz), 127.8 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz), 115.3 (d, *J* = 21.5 Hz), 93.4 (d, *J* = 172.4 Hz), 79.7, 73.7, 52.0, 47.7, 40.1 – 39.0 (m), 37.4 (d, *J* = 21.3 Hz), 35.5 – 34.9 (m), 34.1 – 33.4 (m), 28.4.

d1-¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -114.10 – -114.21 (m, 1F), -163.04 – -163.50 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 3433, 2927, 1735, 1692, 1510, 1433, 1366, 1222, 1156, 838.

HRMS calcd for C₂₁H₂₉F₂NO₅Na [M+Na]⁺ 436.1911; found 436.1934.

Compound **36-d2** was isolated as a colorless oil (35.1 mg, 0.08 mmol, 37%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.20, 7:3 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

d2-¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.34 – 7.29 (m, 2H), 7.10 – 7.05 (m, 2H), 4.77 (d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 3.92 – 3.83 (m, 2H), 3.69 (s, 3H), 3.06 – 2.98 (m, 3H), 2.24 – 2.11 (m, 1H), 1.92 – 1.82 (m, 2H), 1.76 – 1.67 (m, 2H), 1.58 – 1.51 (m, 1H), 1.45 (s, 9H).

d2-¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 175.2, 162.6 (d, *J* = 246.9 Hz), 154.6, 137.3 (d, *J* = 3.2 Hz), 128.1 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz), 115.6 (d, *J* = 21.5 Hz), 93.1 (d, *J* = 172.9 Hz), 79.7, 75.5, 73.7, 52.1, 47.6, 39.8 (d, *J* = 21.5 Hz), 39.5, 34.9 (d, *J* = 21.5 Hz), 33.9 (d, *J* = 20.3 Hz), 28.4.

d2-¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -113.58 – -113.68 (m, 1F), -163.14 – -163.58 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 3433, 2927, 1735, 1692, 1510, 1433, 1366, 1222, 1156, 838.

HRMS calcd for C₂₁H₂₉F₂NO₅Na [M+Na]⁺ 436.1911; found 436.1934.

tert-butyl 4-(2-(butoxycarbonyl)-3-hydroxyonyl)-4-fluoropiperidine-1-carboxylate

Prepared following **GP3** with 1-(tert-butoxycarbonyl)-4-fluoropiperidine-4-carboxylic acid **1c**, butyl acrylate **S1c** and heptanal **S20** as starting materials.

Compound **37** was obtained as a yellow oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr = 50:50, 44%).

Compound **37** was isolated as a colorless oil (mixture of diastereomers, dr = 99:1, 45.0 mg, 0.05 mmol, 22%) after flash column chromatography (SiO₂) (R_f = 0.3, 8:2 hexane/ ethyl acetate).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 4.15 – 4.11 (m, 1H), 3.98 – 3.85 (m, 1H), 3.81 – 3.74 (m, 1H), 3.13 – 2.98 (m, 1H), 2.70 – 2.63 (m, 1H), 2.35 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 2.24 – 2.07 (m, 1H), 2.00 – 1.84 (m, 2H), 1.84 – 1.71 (m, 1H), 1.70 – 1.57 (m, 4H), 1.47 (s, 6H), 1.45 – 1.37 (m, 3H), 1.34 – 1.26 (m, 5H), 0.96 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 3H), 0.92 – 0.87 (m, 2H).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 175.4, 154.7, 93.5 (d, *J* = 172.5 Hz), 79.7, 72.5, 64.8, 45.6, 39.9 – 39.1 (m), 37.3 (d, *J* = 21.6 Hz), 34.4, 34.3 – 34.2 (m), 33.7, 31.7, 30.5, 28.4, 25.7, 22.6, 19.1, 14.0, 13.6.

¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -162.55 – -163.53 (m, 1F).

IR (film)/cm⁻¹ 3456, 2957, 2929, 1732, 1697, 1424, 1366, 1245, 1157, 967.

HRMS calcd for C₂₄H₄₄FNO₅Na [M+Na]⁺ 468.3101; found 468.3077.

8 Mechanistic experiments

8.1 Cyclic Voltammetry Studies

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) was performed on a Metrohm Autolab PGSTAT 302-N potentiostat using a three-electrode cell (a glassy carbon as working electrode, an Ag-wire as quasi-reference electrode, and a platinum counter electrode) and Nova 2.1.6 as software. CV measurements were carried out at 25°C in dry acetonitrile (MeCN) containing tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate (0.10 M) as the supporting electrolyte, with a scan rate of 100 mV/s ranging from -2.2 and +2.8 V, starting at 0 V in the positive scan direction. Oxygen-free conditions were achieved by purging the electrochemical cell with nitrogen gas for 5 minutes before each measurement. Three scans were carried out per measurement, and numerical values were extracted from the third scan. The analyte (acid or its corresponding carboxylate) concentrations ranged between 1.0 and 10 mM. Carboxylates were generated in situ by adding of 1.0 equiv tetrabutylammonium hydroxide solution (1.0 M in methanol, Sigma-Aldrich) to the carboxylic acid. After each experiment, the potential of the Ag electrode was calibrated against the ferrocene/ferrocenium redox couple (for nonaqueous electrochemistry, IUPAC recommends the use of a redox couple such as ferrocene/ferrocenium ion (Fc/Fc⁺) as an internal (or marker) standard.^{11,12}) converted to vs. SCE by adding 380 mV.¹³ Between each set of experiments (consisting of 3 CV scans of analyte and 3 CV scans of analyte with ferrocene) the glassy carbon electrode was mechanically polished in a figure-of-eight motion using an aqueous 0.05 μm alumina slurry on a nylon polishing pad. Then, it was rinsed with deionized water, and dried under a stream of nitrogen gas. All compounds evaluated showed chemically irreversible oxidation waves and, as suggested by Nicewicz and co-workers¹⁴, the oxidation (anodic) potentials are reported as the potentials at half the peak ($E_{p/2}$) instead of anodic peak potentials (E_{pa}).

Figure 5 Cyclic Voltammery of 1a.

Figure 6 Cyclic Voltammery of carboxylate 1a.

Figure 7 Cyclic Voltammery of 1b.

Figure 8 Cyclic Voltammery of carboxylate 1b.

Figure 9 Cyclic Voltammery of 1c.

Figure 10 Cyclic Voltammery of carboxylate 1c.

Figure 11 Cyclic Voltammery of 1d.

Figure 12 Cyclic Voltammery of carboxylate 1d.

Figure 13 Cyclic Voltammery of 1e.

Figure 14 Cyclic Voltammery of carboxylate 1e.

8.2 ON-OFF experiment

To an oven-dried 4 mL vial equipped with a stirring bar were added 2-fluoro-3-phenylpropanoic acid (0.3 mmol, 1.3 equiv.), potassium phosphate tribasic (0.3 mmol, 1.3 equiv.), 4CzIPN (5.9 mg, 2.5 mol%), benzyl methacrylate (0.23 mmol, 1 equiv.), and dry DMSO (1 mL). Subsequently, the vial was sealed with a rubber septum and the solution was sparged with N_2 (1 min) and placed in a PhotoCube™ photochemical reactor equipped with a blue lamp ($\lambda = 457$ nm, 128 W). The solution was stirred and irradiated discontinuously and after each light-phase and each dark phase, an aliquot of 0.02 mL was withdrawn, diluted with AcOEt and analyzed by GC affording the following data.

Time (minutes)	Conversion of S2a (%)	Light
0-45	19	ON
45-90	23	OFF
90-135	43	ON
135-180	45	OFF
180-225	61	ON
225-270	62	OFF
270-315	77	ON
315-360	78	OFF
360-405	90	ON
405-450	91	OFF
450-495	95	ON

Table 6. Results of the ON/OFF experiment.

8.3 Radical Trapping Experiment

TEMPO trapping experiment

To an oven-dried 4 mL vial equipped with a stirring bar were added 2-fluoro-3-phenylpropanoic acid (0.3 mmol, 1.3 equiv.), potassium phosphate tribasic (0.3 mmol, 1.3 equiv.), 4CzIPN (5.9 mg, 2.5 mol%), benzyl methacrylate (0.23 mmol, 1 equiv.), TEMPO (0.69 mmol, 3 eq.) and dry DMSO (0.5 mL). Subsequently, the vial was sealed with a rubber septum and the solution was sparged with N_2 (1 min). The solution was stirred and irradiated in a PhotoCube™ photochemical reactor equipped with a blue lamp ($\lambda = 457$ nm, 128 W) for 16 h. Then the vial was removed from the photochemical reactor. The solution was diluted with 20 mL of AcOEt and transferred to a separatory funnel where it was washed three times with brine. The organic layer was dried over Na_2SO_4 . The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the crude reaction mixture was analyzed by 1H -NMR. The crude NMR showed no formation of product **7**. No TEMPO adduct was detected via NMR or HRMS.

8.4 Computational studies

Computational methods

All calculations were performed using ORCA (v. 5.0.1).¹⁵ Geometry optimisations and frequency calculations for were obtained at the ω B97X-D3/def2-SVP level of theory.¹⁶ Single point energies were then refined at the SMD(DMSO)- ω B97X-D3/def2-TZVP level of theory on the optimised structures.¹⁷ Stationary points for the redox potential calculations were refined at the SMD(DMSO)-M06-2X/ma-def2-TZVP// ω B97X-D3/def2-SVP level. The vibrational analysis identified stationary points as either minima (no imaginary frequencies) or transition states (singular large imaginary frequencies) and were used to calculate thermal corrections (298.15K, 1 atm). All open-shell systems were calculated using unrestricted formalism. Vibrational entropies were computed according to the QRRHO of S. Grimme.¹⁸

The standard reduction potentials were calculated using the reported equation where ΔG° are the standard free energy change associated with the reduction process (1 M), F is the Faraday constant (96485 C mol⁻¹) and n is the number of electrons transferred:

$$E^0 = \frac{-\Delta G^0}{nF}$$

The free energy of the electron is based on the ion convention formalism is -0.04 eV.¹⁹ The reduction potentials were referenced to the standard calomel electrode (SCE, 0.244 V) itself referenced to the standard hydrogen electrode (further correction of 4.28 eV). ΔG for the reduction of Giese products by 4CzIPN⁻ was obtained from the aforementioned equation using the corresponding cell potentials.²⁰ Structures were visualized using Avogadro and Chemcraft software.

Table 7. Global nucleophilicity index

The geometries employed in the philicity study were obtained at the ω B97X-D3/def2-TZVP level of theory and assessed as minima through vibrational analysis. Electronic affinity and ionization energy were computed at the ω B97X-D3/def2-TZVP level of theory using unrestricted formalism. ω (electrophilicity indexes) are defined as $\omega = \mu/2\eta$, where μ (electronic chemical potential) and η (chemical hardness) were computed as functions of vertical ionization potentials and electron affinities.²¹ $\omega < 1.5$ eV are related to nucleophilic radicals.⁷

	Electron Affinity (eV)	Ionization Energy (eV)	μ	η	ω
CH ₂ F·	-0,89	9,54	-4,33	10,43	0,90
CH ₃ CHF·	-0,26	9,59	-4,67	9,85	1,11
PhCHF·	-0,47	7,20	-3,84	6,73	1,09
PhCH ₂ CHF·	-0,51	8,26	-3,88	8,77	0,86

For a comparison with nucleophilicity indices calculated for other radicals, see Chem. Sci., 2024, 15, 11337-11346.

Cartesian coordinates

CH₂F·

6	-10.595920000	4.500910000	0.090010000
1	-10.748800000	5.368000000	0.720390000
1	-10.749520000	3.476530000	0.405920000
9	-10.790140000	4.718510000	-1.216320000

CH₃CHF·

6	-10.347220000	4.312920000	-0.197950000
6	-10.728000000	5.459930000	0.720580000
1	-10.539940000	3.342520000	0.306160000
9	-11.085720000	4.378390000	-1.365140000
1	-10.524950000	6.427010000	0.215040000
1	-10.126410000	5.405260000	1.651670000
1	-11.806510000	5.398930000	0.978090000

PhCHF·

6	-7.690718000	2.111514000	1.920106000
6	-6.985893000	2.245055000	3.143029000
1	-7.542125000	2.272073000	4.074504000
6	-5.610690000	2.341337000	3.151253000
1	-5.086002000	2.445224000	4.094860000
6	-4.890649000	2.307111000	1.954945000
1	-3.809544000	2.383879000	1.967596000
6	-5.571070000	2.174130000	0.744413000
1	-5.013702000	2.147205000	-0.185852000
6	-6.948044000	2.076792000	0.714312000
1	-7.473023000	1.973024000	-0.227344000
6	-9.086098000	2.020670000	1.938106000
9	-9.769078000	1.904585000	0.789494000
1	-9.713593000	2.036651000	2.819398000

PhCH₂CHF·

9	-12.509120000	5.000410000	-0.211060000
6	-10.280860000	5.324580000	0.617150000
1	-11.282900000	3.389630000	-0.040080000
6	-11.274630000	4.474000000	-0.088930000
6	-10.089320000	6.679710000	-0.033380000
6	-10.568060000	7.835860000	0.570410000
1	-11.079400000	7.766970000	1.525510000
6	-10.401530000	9.074790000	-0.038750000
1	-10.781720000	9.968500000	0.444250000
6	-9.752100000	9.166870000	-1.261430000
1	-9.620240000	10.132130000	-1.737900000

6	-9.271720000	8.014040000	-1.873760000
1	-8.764040000	8.078170000	-2.830240000
6	-9.441830000	6.780490000	-1.263110000
1	-9.072150000	5.881110000	-1.746280000
1	-9.334030000	4.776740000	0.635680000
1	-10.586130000	5.467440000	1.664270000

Table 8. Differences in Gibbs free energy (ΔG), electronic energy (ΔE), zero-point energy (ΔZPE), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy ($T\Delta S$) computed at the optimization level of theory ($\omega B97X-D3/def2-SVP$). ΔE , ΔH and ΔG at the single-point level of theory (SMD(DMSO)- $\omega B97X-D3/def2-TZVP$ or SMD(DMSO)-M06-2X/ma-def2-TZVP) were obtained using thermal corrections from the optimization level. Energies are reported in kcal mol⁻¹ Gibbs free energies were calculated at standard conditions (298.15 K and 1 M). E^0 are expressed versus SCE.

System	$\omega B97X-D3/def2-SVP$					SMD(DMSO)- $\omega B97X-D3/def2-TZVP$			
	ΔE	ΔZPE	ΔH	$T\Delta S$	ΔG	ΔE	ΔH	ΔG (1atm)	ΔG (1M)
I TS	-4,7	1,2	-3,9	-14,1	10,2	-1,3	-0,4	13,7	11,8
I adduct	-43,6	3,5	-40,7	-14,8	-25,9	-39,4	-36,6	-21,8	-23,6
II TS	0,6	1,2	1,4	-17,7	14,5	3,3	4,0	17,1	15,2
II adduct	-35,6	3,0	-33,1	-17,7	-20,0	-32,2	-29,7	-16,6	-18,5
III TS	-0,5	1,0	0,2	-11,6	14,6	3,5	4,1	18,5	16,6
III adduct	-39,2	3,6	-36,1	-11,7	-21,6	-33,5	-30,5	-15,9	-17,8

Process	SMD(DMSO)-M06-2X/ma-def2-TZVP				
	ΔE	ΔH	ΔG (1atm)	ΔG (1M)	E^0 vs SCE
Red-1	-2,87	-2,94	-2,94	-3,02	-1,50
Red-2	-3,51	-3,55	-3,54	-3,62	-0,90
Red-3	-2,28	-2,35	-2,34	-2,42	-2,10
Red-4	-2,22	-2,30	-2,30	-2,38	-2,14
Red-4CzIPN					-1.21 ^(a)

(a) Reference value: Nature 492, 234–238, 2012.

Cartesian coordinates

Methyl acrylate

6	-1.301710000	-0.693140000	0.029850000
6	-0.036980000	0.094610000	-0.038090000
8	0.035250000	1.294820000	-0.138350000
8	1.037980000	-0.707600000	0.030960000
1	-1.205330000	-1.778760000	0.119110000
6	-2.482240000	-0.073910000	-0.017440000
1	-3.423580000	-0.628390000	0.031620000
1	-2.522490000	1.016450000	-0.106860000
6	2.300900000	-0.051940000	-0.022300000
1	2.406240000	0.658090000	0.812000000
1	2.411930000	0.502310000	-0.966720000
1	3.060330000	-0.840460000	0.049310000

Propene

6	-7.587490000	1.685550000	0.124550000
6	-6.838870000	2.752690000	-0.159790000
6	-7.271410000	4.182270000	0.003900000
1	-7.236350000	4.717620000	-0.959950000
1	-6.598880000	4.721350000	0.692340000
1	-8.296540000	4.250420000	0.399210000
1	-7.210990000	0.667930000	-0.018250000
1	-8.607670000	1.790330000	0.511820000
1	-5.822620000	2.595580000	-0.546180000

tButyl vinyl ether

6	-5.763270000	-1.335090000	0.023250000
6	-5.043380000	-0.210600000	0.026650000
8	-5.573390000	0.991920000	-0.289550000
6	-4.732620000	2.161950000	-0.264880000
6	-4.198310000	2.401320000	1.150450000
6	-5.673890000	3.290960000	-0.677630000
6	-3.594990000	2.017660000	-1.279700000
1	-5.033030000	2.447370000	1.866350000
1	-3.647450000	3.353550000	1.192230000
1	-3.511240000	1.603160000	1.470520000
1	-6.511640000	3.361800000	0.032000000
1	-6.085740000	3.090700000	-1.677970000
1	-5.142300000	4.254390000	-0.698170000
1	-2.897150000	1.212880000	-1.002780000
1	-3.018790000	2.953750000	-1.339260000
1	-4.004470000	1.793330000	-2.276450000
1	-5.290740000	-2.283340000	0.285180000

1	-6.824290000	-1.322010000	-0.239730000
1	-3.978430000	-0.222280000	0.289630000

PhCH₂CHF· (radical)

9	-12.597930000	5.311700000	0.452690000
6	-10.198050000	5.246210000	0.489950000
1	-11.660280000	3.524160000	0.160670000
6	-11.499230000	4.608460000	0.133990000
6	-10.026670000	6.626690000	-0.116820000
6	-10.697900000	7.726540000	0.431610000
1	-11.331360000	7.585250000	1.311830000
6	-10.570850000	8.993070000	-0.138710000
1	-11.101680000	9.842350000	0.301050000
6	-9.768520000	9.177840000	-1.266750000
1	-9.667280000	10.171210000	-1.713010000
6	-9.096590000	8.087580000	-1.820930000
1	-8.465730000	8.222800000	-2.704240000
6	-9.228220000	6.820560000	-1.249160000
1	-8.700610000	5.968400000	-1.689370000
1	-9.389990000	4.577110000	0.156120000
1	-10.108870000	5.321520000	1.593440000

PhCH₂CHF⁻ (anion)

9	-12.128750000	5.421510000	1.697360000
6	-10.321740000	5.157680000	0.195910000
1	-11.755210000	3.702190000	0.683590000
6	-11.794090000	4.782800000	0.381770000
6	-10.091010000	6.569380000	-0.313840000
6	-10.935020000	7.609030000	0.115640000
1	-11.744370000	7.334600000	0.796430000
6	-10.740020000	8.916900000	-0.326980000
1	-11.411040000	9.711750000	0.018720000
6	-9.698530000	9.224250000	-1.211610000
1	-9.548270000	10.253090000	-1.557250000
6	-8.857170000	8.201830000	-1.650560000
1	-8.042500000	8.423020000	-2.349880000
6	-9.058490000	6.890050000	-1.204750000
1	-8.395490000	6.090650000	-1.556700000
1	-9.864830000	4.451750000	-0.524960000
1	-9.723220000	5.070960000	1.139460000

TS-I

6	-2.604195000	1.289702000	2.977836000
6	-2.686499000	1.888624000	1.629058000
8	-2.818059000	3.071691000	1.397546000

8	-2.606356000	0.957250000	0.665486000	6	-5.942720000	1.031920000	0.351320000
1	-2.627577000	0.200357000	3.045108000	6	-5.837460000	1.544850000	2.724670000
6	-2.580495000	2.091645000	4.068325000	6	-4.439410000	2.518250000	4.642860000
1	-2.461486000	1.677328000	5.072571000	1	-5.976440000	1.379150000	-0.685470000
1	-2.439975000	3.167230000	3.931867000	6	-5.884600000	1.963220000	1.389610000
6	-2.694026000	1.439331000	-0.668726000	6	-5.743370000	2.553840000	3.847620000
1	-1.850484000	2.108747000	-0.897928000	1	-6.565540000	2.397310000	4.565430000
1	-3.632069000	1.993211000	-0.819686000	1	-5.848040000	3.031240000	1.156640000
1	-2.666764000	0.554921000	-1.317616000	1	-5.860450000	3.571880000	3.443870000
1	-5.708192000	-1.900102000	2.637074000	1	-4.469440000	3.321980000	5.399240000
6	-5.773258000	-0.895181000	2.209754000	1	-2.830910000	0.516560000	3.266530000
9	-5.263024000	1.773049000	5.559086000	1	-3.212990000	3.609430000	3.234570000
1	-6.070031000	-1.603222000	0.187152000	1	-2.323650000	2.766870000	4.526160000
6	-5.975885000	-0.730625000	0.839521000				
1	-5.490511000	0.072622000	4.115379000				
6	-5.651000000	0.216117000	3.046291000				
6	-6.059248000	0.558125000	0.309887000				
6	-5.715771000	1.513149000	2.522084000				
6	-4.816351000	2.669964000	4.652924000				
1	-6.218380000	0.702269000	-0.762920000				
6	-5.927632000	1.666898000	1.145288000				
6	-5.586445000	2.761551000	3.377418000				
1	-6.606538000	3.128974000	3.616335000				
1	-4.512544000	3.603816000	5.143300000				
1	-5.970371000	2.674802000	0.720706000				
1	-5.104012000	3.550302000	2.778910000				

Adduct-I⁻ (radical)

6	-2.892250000	1.539230000	2.890420000
6	-2.713030000	1.773570000	1.466030000
8	-2.762530000	2.865370000	0.931440000
8	-2.490480000	0.632160000	0.784650000
6	-3.163640000	2.673880000	3.812280000
6	-2.352960000	0.776580000	-0.621480000
1	-1.496140000	1.422360000	-0.868630000
1	-3.260980000	1.221180000	-1.056450000
1	-2.196480000	-0.233570000	-1.020870000
1	-5.928230000	-1.831080000	2.196080000
6	-5.917040000	-0.762220000	1.964250000
9	-4.364180000	1.315900000	5.344260000
1	-5.993430000	-1.064690000	-0.177340000
6	-5.953500000	-0.333670000	0.635230000
1	-5.830230000	-0.167880000	4.038880000
6	-5.867080000	0.168890000	3.000230000

Adduct-I⁻ (anion)

6	-2.517392000	1.581681000	2.875863000
6	-2.578760000	2.125633000	1.609202000
8	-2.981072000	3.260748000	1.248763000
8	-2.148387000	1.238807000	0.593400000
6	-2.913832000	2.419445000	4.053309000
6	-2.281589000	1.719961000	-0.710648000
1	-1.875006000	2.739236000	-0.827277000
1	-3.337224000	1.756810000	-1.048566000
1	-1.734478000	1.023890000	-1.370630000
1	-7.314045000	-1.696394000	2.852713000
6	-6.803514000	-0.853925000	2.373484000
9	-4.656976000	1.216369000	5.211977000
1	-6.828503000	-1.754766000	0.403520000
6	-6.533334000	-0.887993000	1.004375000
1	-6.625345000	0.269215000	4.212195000
6	-6.422530000	0.250734000	3.138917000
6	-5.876203000	0.193330000	0.411314000
6	-5.755403000	1.336094000	2.554095000
6	-4.378110000	2.392544000	4.497161000
1	-5.642744000	0.174973000	-0.658289000
6	-5.494535000	1.293713000	1.177335000
6	-5.398369000	2.567008000	3.363921000
1	-6.334474000	2.962531000	3.798321000
1	-4.946678000	2.128423000	0.730291000
1	-4.981299000	3.327607000	2.686149000
1	-4.537475000	3.214841000	5.224191000
1	-2.194095000	0.546635000	3.003714000
1	-2.705156000	3.480419000	3.816103000
1	-2.320673000	2.174941000	4.957127000

TS-II

6	-5.172650000	-2.161400000	2.362210000
6	-5.636060000	-0.901290000	2.137780000
6	-6.971140000	-0.383520000	2.584780000
1	-4.274980000	-2.518670000	1.850100000
1	-5.839520000	-2.929410000	2.765920000
1	-4.987110000	-0.191860000	1.607050000
1	-9.929940000	-2.080410000	6.157510000
1	-8.816440000	0.126170000	6.516270000
6	-8.850730000	-1.977420000	6.013460000
6	-8.227670000	-0.744780000	6.214220000
9	-3.922020000	-3.657940000	4.500880000
6	-8.082800000	-3.079500000	5.632310000
1	-8.559460000	-4.052180000	5.479410000
6	-6.852080000	-0.617670000	6.018650000
1	-6.373590000	0.356400000	6.163890000
6	-6.705550000	-2.950590000	5.444020000
6	-6.074610000	-1.711790000	5.619870000
6	-3.951170000	-2.314490000	4.297490000
1	-6.112990000	-3.818490000	5.148980000
6	-4.583360000	-1.528820000	5.404290000
1	-2.983410000	-1.960010000	3.919310000
1	-4.051830000	-1.766710000	6.348550000
1	-4.379030000	-0.466440000	5.198010000
1	-6.866030000	0.476370000	3.268430000
1	-7.553570000	-1.156380000	3.108150000
1	-7.559160000	-0.028990000	1.719820000

Adduct-II (radical)

6	-5.304000000	-1.908860000	2.791500000
6	-5.342670000	-0.434270000	2.558540000
6	-6.581300000	0.239450000	2.072810000
1	-4.996400000	-2.450040000	1.872670000
1	-6.309840000	-2.284260000	3.044470000
1	-4.392670000	0.113940000	2.538730000
1	-9.867870000	-2.488300000	6.602570000
1	-9.044450000	-0.211850000	5.996400000
6	-8.815760000	-2.333820000	6.346710000
6	-8.355080000	-1.061280000	6.006380000
9	-4.353200000	-3.713580000	3.981380000
6	-7.923890000	-3.408870000	6.359590000
1	-8.277170000	-4.409090000	6.626980000
6	-7.010930000	-0.869050000	5.678960000
1	-6.654350000	0.129590000	5.407380000

6	-6.582130000	-3.213690000	6.030760000
6	-6.109540000	-1.940290000	5.684200000
6	-4.340000000	-2.322990000	3.897290000
1	-5.889390000	-4.059070000	6.025690000
6	-4.668410000	-1.741410000	5.273280000
1	-3.309070000	-2.031160000	3.625170000
1	-3.990080000	-2.212930000	6.002620000
1	-4.430200000	-0.666580000	5.254000000
1	-6.504420000	1.336180000	2.127610000
1	-7.461760000	-0.078450000	2.659240000
1	-6.802330000	-0.019110000	1.016470000

Adduct-II (anion)

6	-5.467850000	-1.592620000	2.760470000
6	-5.400250000	-0.078500000	2.910550000
6	-6.210860000	0.575730000	1.802890000
1	-5.197340000	-2.001200000	1.745440000
1	-6.505400000	-1.952960000	2.929310000
1	-4.332890000	0.227530000	2.784510000
1	-9.814600000	-2.672040000	7.034470000
1	-9.255630000	-0.681350000	5.633890000
6	-8.792310000	-2.524250000	6.669230000
6	-8.475410000	-1.408070000	5.886140000
9	-4.777650000	-3.719560000	3.651120000
6	-7.797270000	-3.454440000	6.973360000
1	-8.035080000	-4.336390000	7.578220000
6	-7.177080000	-1.214980000	5.413770000
1	-6.872240000	-0.374730000	4.758620000
6	-6.494780000	-3.261760000	6.501610000
6	-6.168860000	-2.141210000	5.730130000
6	-4.578060000	-2.327250000	3.748310000
1	-5.715430000	-3.996260000	6.731660000
6	-4.768130000	-1.922020000	5.208870000
1	-3.516550000	-2.154510000	3.484770000
1	-4.046530000	-2.481630000	5.829540000
1	-4.536110000	-0.846760000	5.243000000
1	-6.126900000	1.680800000	1.821690000
1	-7.295820000	0.351960000	1.904550000
1	-5.957910000	0.266680000	0.745260000

TS-III

8	-6.251826000	-0.407530000	2.297427000
6	-6.499297000	1.012407000	2.281644000
6	-5.506332000	1.739542000	3.192528000

6	-7.914384000	1.136983000	2.839710000	1	-5.848820000	1.226820000	0.095110000
6	-6.430967000	1.532662000	0.843331000	1	-6.496830000	2.848830000	0.462650000
1	-5.558079000	1.321511000	4.208360000	1	-7.463230000	1.390500000	0.833260000
1	-5.757649000	2.809997000	3.241858000	1	-5.037420000	-2.690930000	1.834790000
1	-4.471809000	1.657176000	2.825772000	1	-6.412480000	-2.179050000	2.836260000
1	-7.955831000	0.714465000	3.853969000	1	-4.365690000	-0.307020000	1.416010000
1	-8.619080000	0.578921000	2.205062000	1	-9.929710000	-2.994770000	6.660500000
1	-8.225407000	2.192312000	2.874598000	1	-9.625620000	-0.903590000	5.334640000
1	-5.418252000	1.437530000	0.421811000	6	-8.929130000	-2.681780000	6.348360000
1	-6.710743000	2.596846000	0.809450000	6	-8.757860000	-1.511440000	5.607800000
1	-7.126012000	0.966693000	0.204531000	9	-4.492630000	-3.569160000	4.099140000
1	-3.827251000	-2.570558000	1.577643000	6	-7.814060000	-3.452150000	6.686130000
1	-5.554172000	-2.929688000	2.192271000	1	-7.938540000	-4.372430000	7.264490000
1	-4.299294000	-0.151646000	1.590836000	6	-7.479960000	-1.112300000	5.210450000
1	-9.596889000	-0.719483000	6.351887000	1	-7.345660000	-0.207150000	4.612960000
1	-7.787277000	0.721639000	7.301291000	6	-6.538800000	-3.052010000	6.286830000
6	-8.550412000	-0.906477000	6.094732000	6	-6.355030000	-1.875530000	5.548390000
6	-7.538921000	-0.101325000	6.624607000	6	-4.502130000	-2.201060000	3.839220000
9	-4.489495000	-3.921234000	4.466899000	1	-5.669120000	-3.663410000	6.542520000
6	-8.211408000	-1.952389000	5.236925000	6	-4.969980000	-1.468330000	5.096570000
1	-8.994185000	-2.590724000	4.817215000	1	-3.458200000	-1.910160000	3.620910000
6	-6.207756000	-0.349964000	6.293046000	1	-4.241690000	-1.676930000	5.896720000
1	-5.419236000	0.280802000	6.717755000	1	-4.938730000	-0.389090000	4.887890000
6	-6.876301000	-2.196922000	4.906407000				
6	-5.855499000	-1.395785000	5.426590000				
6	-3.993775000	-2.691820000	4.169292000				
1	-6.628198000	-3.027347000	4.246309000				
6	-4.382904000	-1.600250000	5.115204000				
1	-2.927344000	-2.756462000	3.915611000				
1	-3.851543000	-1.747247000	6.077429000				
1	-3.974817000	-0.665728000	4.691551000				

Adduct-III' (radical)

8	-5.866020000	0.398770000	2.709950000
6	-5.830000000	1.752970000	2.215030000
6	-4.392500000	2.281320000	2.218810000
6	-6.683590000	2.532930000	3.212230000
6	-6.444760000	1.807200000	0.814950000
1	-3.946730000	2.167430000	3.219120000
1	-4.385880000	3.350090000	1.956190000
1	-3.756930000	1.756700000	1.490160000
1	-6.257790000	2.453310000	4.224150000
1	-7.707170000	2.129420000	3.233700000
1	-6.730230000	3.596460000	2.933520000

Adduct-III' (anion)

6	-4.986885000	-1.824895000	2.574876000
6	-4.610359000	-0.427659000	2.084246000
8	-5.187626000	0.554592000	3.047442000
6	-5.781479000	1.684118000	2.439441000
6	-4.751471000	2.418434000	1.569767000
6	-6.238018000	2.585944000	3.591678000
6	-6.974702000	1.253303000	1.574429000
1	-3.896005000	2.733765000	2.191076000
1	-5.187056000	3.307702000	1.080371000
1	-4.389346000	1.700543000	0.817639000
1	-5.374050000	2.854206000	4.221496000
1	-6.970131000	2.060098000	4.226052000
1	-6.705682000	3.511913000	3.214925000
1	-6.593397000	0.462710000	0.906840000
1	-7.390880000	2.092155000	0.989360000
1	-7.776936000	0.831378000	2.204030000
1	-4.609649000	-2.558612000	1.836542000
1	-6.084843000	-1.962903000	2.601472000
1	-3.503923000	-0.332522000	2.233332000

1	-10.178756000	-2.650781000	6.042663000
1	-9.522026000	-0.689518000	4.639571000
6	-9.121376000	-2.426560000	5.867227000
6	-8.752795000	-1.327888000	5.086304000
9	-4.604005000	-3.655371000	4.124915000
6	-8.128317000	-3.241999000	6.415080000
1	-8.405310000	-4.112555000	7.019221000
6	-7.404881000	-1.043032000	4.862516000
1	-7.088215000	-0.209118000	4.231351000
6	-6.780803000	-2.953289000	6.188910000
6	-6.400535000	-1.845910000	5.420013000
6	-4.404605000	-2.267852000	3.917852000
1	-6.003399000	-3.602023000	6.603835000
6	-4.944084000	-1.546284000	5.153007000
1	-3.309078000	-2.120564000	3.878510000
1	-4.345661000	-1.851823000	6.028854000
1	-4.807406000	-0.470915000	4.971425000

9 Copies of NMR spectra

8
¹⁹F NMR
 (CDCl₃, 377 MHz)

9
¹H NMR
 (CDCl₃, 400 MHz)

12
 ^{19}F NMR
 (CDCl_3 , 377 MHz)

13
 ^1H NMR
 (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz)

14
¹⁹F NMR
 (CDCl₃, 377 MHz)

15
¹H NMR
 (CDCl₃, 400 MHz)

15
¹³C NMR
(CDCl₃, 101 MHz)

15
¹⁹F NMR
(CDCl₃, 377 MHz)

16
¹⁹F NMR
 (CDCl₃, 377 MHz)

8.57
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2.09
2.08
2.08
2.07
2.06

17
¹H NMR
 (CDCl₃, 400 MHz)

19
 ^{13}C NMR
 (CDCl_3 , 101 MHz)

19
 ^{19}F NMR
 (CDCl_3 , 377 MHz)

20
¹H NMR
 (CDCl₃, 400 MHz)

20
¹³C NMR
 (CDCl₃, 101 MHz)

20
¹⁹F NMR
 (CDCl₃, 377 MHz)

21
¹H NMR
 (CDCl₃, 400 MHz)

23
¹³C NMR
 (CDCl₃, 101 MHz)

23
¹⁹F NMR
 (CDCl₃, 377 MHz)

25
¹³C NMR
(CDCl₃, 101 MHz)

25
¹⁹F NMR
(CDCl₃, 377 MHz)

26
¹⁹F NMR
 (CDCl₃, 377 MHz)

27
¹H NMR
 (CDCl₃, 400 MHz)

27
¹³C NMR
(CDCl₃, 101 MHz)

27
¹⁹F NMR
(CDCl₃, 377 MHz)

28
¹⁹F NMR
 (CDCl₃, 377 MHz)

29
¹H NMR
 (CDCl₃, 400 MHz)

30
¹H NMR
 (CDCl₃, 400 MHz)

30
¹³C NMR
 (CDCl₃, 101 MHz)

30
 ^{19}F NMR
 (CDCl_3 , 377 MHz)

31
 ^1H NMR
 (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz)

32
¹⁹F NMR
 (CDCl₃, 377 MHz)

33
¹H NMR
 (CDCl₃, 400 MHz)

34
 ^{19}F NMR
 (CDCl_3 , 377 MHz)

35
 ^1H NMR
 (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz)

36-d1
 ^{19}F NMR
 (CDCl_3 , 377 MHz)

36-d2
 ^1H NMR
 (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz)

37
¹H NMR
 (CDCl₃, 400 MHz)

37
¹³C NMR
 (CDCl₃, 101 MHz)

37
¹⁹F NMR
(CDCl₃, 377 MHz)

10 Author contribution

M. C. and R. L. designed the project. F. P., Y. G., and D. S. performed most of the experiments with input from L. D., M. C., and R. L. M. A. carried out the computational investigations. G. R. performed cyclic voltammetry analysis. All authors contributed to the writing and editing of the manuscript. The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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